

Comparison of Model and Satellite Data used in the Air Quality Stripes Project

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Project website: <https://airqualitystripes.info>

About the data: <https://airqualitystripes.info/about/>

The Air Quality Stripes combines particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, ug m⁻³) data from a global model with satellite observations of PM_{2.5} to create a historical time series (1850-2022). This document shows the model and satellite data for each city before and after the merging and bias correction step.

Satellite data: A dataset that combines ground-level and satellite observations of PM_{2.5} concentrations from [Van Donkelaar et al \(2021, V5 0.1 degree resolution\)](#) is used. This dataset can be found [here](#).

Model data: Satellite observations of PM_{2.5} aren't available for the years before 1998, so instead historical trends in air pollution concentrations are taken from the UKESM a computer model ([Turnock 2020](#)) which provided data to the [Coupled Model Intercomparison Project \(CMIP6\)](#).

Merging: CMIP6 multi-model simulations tend to underestimate PM_{2.5} concentrations compared to global observations ([Turnock et al., 2020](#)). To address this issue and to ensure a smooth time series between the model and satellite data, we take the following steps:

- 1) For each city, we first calculate a three-year (2000-2002) mean of the satellite data for that city.
- 2) Next, we calculate the three-year (2000-2002) mean of model concentrations for the same city. The ratio between these values (data ratio) represents the model's bias compared to observations.
- 3) This data ratio for each city is used to weight the historical model data to create a combined dataset.

Data Ratio = 3 year average PM_{2.5} from satellite / 3 year average PM_{2.5} from model

This is a similar approach to that taken by [Turnock et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Reddington et al. \(2023\)](#). The satellite data has a larger uncertainty for the years at the start of their time

series as there are fewer ground observations to constrain values to, for this reason we merge time series in 2000 (not 1998).

Sensitivity to the number of years used to calculate the data ratio is found to be low, a three year average gives an average (over all cities) data ratio of 2.6 and a ten year average gives an average (over all cities) data ratio of 2.7.

Overall, the model tends to underestimate PM_{2.5} values compared to satellite observations, and several factors contribute to this discrepancy. First, the model is designed for large-scale global studies rather than detailed city-scale analyses. With a resolution of approximately 1 x 1 degree the model's grid boxes cover large areas, which can cause the high concentrations in urban areas to be "smeared" or averaged out. Second, the emissions data used to drive the model are focused on capturing regional trends rather than city-level emission details, which may lead to an underrepresentation of localized sources. Finally, the model does not account for nitrate aerosols, which can significantly increase total PM_{2.5} concentrations. Future work will investigate how these biases vary across different CMIP models and examine the role of regional effects, such as wildfire smoke or dust emissions.

References

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PM2.5 Timeseries

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